

Nyingma (rnying ma)

also known as “Ancient”

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Tibetan Buddhism, Tantric Buddhism, Buddhist Traditions

The Nyingma, or “Ancient” lineage refers to the oldest of the four major lineages of Tibetan Buddhism. Distinguished from followers of the later Sarma (Tibetan: *gsar ma*) lineages, which includes the Kadam, Sakya, Kagyu, and later Gelug, Nyingma refers to those who adhere to the earliest (pre-tenth century) translations of Buddhist teachings arriving in Tibet, as well as a series of treasure (T: *gter ma*) text revealed from the eleventh century onwards. Renowned for their adherence to a range of esoteric, predominantly tantric Buddhist practices, as well as unorthodox behavior, Nyingma followers served as motivation for periodic reforms throughout Tibetan history, each allegedly “returning” to the ethical roots and meditative discipline of Indian Buddhism. According to the Nyingma lineage, the primordial teacher is Samantabhadra (T: *kun tu bzang po*). Depicted without clothing and vivid blue in color, he represents the untainted wisdom of the all Buddhas of the three times and ten directions. In human form, the Nyingma lineage finds its roots in the Indian master Padmasambhava (T: *pad+ma 'byung gnas*) who is credited with introducing the first coherent and comprehensive presentation of the Buddhist path to Tibet. He is often referenced along with Shantarakshita (Sanskrit: Śāntarakṣita), the great Indian pandit, and Vairotsana (T: *bai ro tsa na*), the great translator, delineating the three most important early Nyingma thinkers. The historical center of the lineage is found in Samye (T: *bsam yas*) monastery in central Tibet. Constructed in the eighth century, Samye monastery was the first successfully constructed monastery in Tibet. After years of wrestling with demons, King Trisong Detsen (T: *khri srong lde btsan*), requested Padmasambhava to subjugate the antagonistic demon, which he did, and the monastery was miraculously completed overnight. Renowned today for their erudite descriptions of the Great Completeness (T: *rdzogs pa chen po*) meditative system, the Nyingma lineage experienced a resurgence in the fourteenth century with the renowned scholar-yogi Longchen Rabjam (T: *klong chen rab 'byams*). Longchenpa, as he is commonly referred to, both revealed new treasure teachings and consolidated much of the existent tantric materials found within the early Nyingma lineage. His extensive writings on topics such as the nine vehicles (T: *they pa dgu*; a defining religious shema of the Nyingma, the subtle body, meditation practice, and most importantly the Great Completeness, revived the Nyingma lineage during and after his life. Extending across the Tibetan plateau to include all three Tibetan states (Utsang, Kham, and Amdo), as well as Bhutan and modern-day Indian state of Ladakh, the Nyingma lineage flourished in many sub-lineages throughout the centuries, resulting in a vibrant array of contemplative and scholarly practices.

Date Range: 700 CE - 1959 CE

Region: Tibetan Plateau.

Region tags: Asia, Himalayas, Tibet (historical)

The area within which the majority of residents adhere to what is broadly understood as Himalayan Buddhism

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: 'Jigs-bral-ye-śes-rdo-rje, Bdud-'joms. *The Nyingma School of Tibetan Buddhism : Its Fundamentals and History* / Dudjom Rinpoche, Jikdrel Yeshe Dorje ; Translated and Edited by Gyurme Dorje in Colaboration with Matthew Kapstein. Wisdom Publications, 1991.
- Source 2: Khetsun Sangpo, Jeffrey. Hopkins, and Anne C. Klein. *Tantric Practice in Nying-Ma / Khetsun Sangpo Rinbochay* ; Translated and Edited by Jeffrey Hopkins ; Co-Edited by Anne Klein. Ithaca, N.Y., USA: Snow Lion Publications, 1982. Print.
- Source 3: Van Schaik, Sam. *Tibet : a History* / Sam Van Schaik. Yale University Press, 2011.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: www.rigpawiki.org
- Source 1 Description: An encyclopedia of figures, groups, terms, and practices included within Tibetan Buddhism at large, with a particular focus on the Nyingma lineage.
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.lotsawahouse.org/>
- Source 2 Description: Lotsawa House is a virtual library of translations from Tibetan, including works by Indian Buddhist masters preserved in the Tibetan language.
- Source 3 URL: <http://www.thlib.org/>
- Source 3 Description: The Tibetan and Himalayan Library (THL) is a publisher of websites, information services, and networking facilities relating to the Tibetan plateau and southern Himalayan regions. Read more: <http://www.thlib.org/about/wiki/thdl%20home%20overview.html#ixzz6UGzIA3i7>

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://bdrc.io/>
- Source 1 Description: The Buddhist Digital Resource Center is a nonprofit organization dedicated to seeking out, preserving, documenting, and disseminating Buddhist literature.
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.lotsawahouse.org/>
- Source 2 Description: Lotsawa House is a virtual library of translations from Tibetan, including works by Indian Buddhist masters preserved in the Tibetan language.
- Source 3 URL: <https://84000.co/>
- Source 3 Description: 84000: Translating the Words of the Buddha is a global non-profit initiative to translate all of the Buddha's words into modern languages, and to make them available to everyone.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: Throughout history, the four major lineages/sects of Tibetan Buddhism—Nyingma, Kagyu, Sakya, Gelug—have competed for both religious and secular power in Tibet. In many historical time periods and/or geographical locations, the Nyingma lineage has existed on the fringes of the religious orthodoxy due, in large part, on their lack of central authority.

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: Depending on the historical era there is a varying degree of accommodation and/or pluralism in regard to Tibetan Buddhism, particularly during the Ecumenical movement (ris med) of the eighteenth and nineteenth centuries. In the case of the Nyingma lineage, the accommodation of other approaches/lineages/schools in Tibetan Buddhism is couched in a superiority of origins. This is to say, while the Nyingma lineage is flexible, it still cites itself as the oldest and/or original lineage of Tibetan Buddhism.

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

Notes: At times.

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: Throughout Tibetan history, there have been numerous religious conflicts between the lineages and/or sects. This does not exclude the Nyingma lineage. For example, in traditional presentations of Tibetan history, many of the earliest adherents to the Nyingma lineage in Central Tibet are said to have experienced persecution at the hands of Langdarma (glang dar ma), the ninth-century Tibetan monarch who violently opposed the growing Buddhist influence in Tibet.

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Notes: Throughout Tibetan history, there has been conflict with surrounding peoples, culminating with the eventual clashes in the 1950s that lead to the Tibetan diaspora. Many of these clashes were dependent on religious affiliation. For example, during the twelfth to fourteenth centuries, the Mongol rulers of modern-day China who sided with the Sakya and Kagyu lineages (depending on the particular era) persecuted Nyingma adherents throughout Tibet, leading to considerable conflict. Later, Nyingma monasteries in Eastern Tibet were persecuted in the fifteenth and sixteenth centuries by the religious orthodoxy from central Tibet, again leading to considerable conflict. .

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– Yes

Notes: Historically, when a child was born in the Himalayan region, she was soon taken to the local religious priest (bla ma) to receive a name and, in turn, be accepted into the religious order of their family.

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: As outlined above, the entrance into any of the Tibetan Buddhist lineages is marked by a ritual of taking refuge (skyabs su 'gro ba) in the three jewels (dkon mchog gsum). While this ritual signifies the entrance into the Buddhist path at large, there is assumed affiliation with the specific lineage—Nyingma, Kagyu, Sakya, Gelug—of the priest who is administering the ritual.

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: Tibetan Buddhism in general, and the Nyingma lineage specifically does not proselytize. However, they are welcoming of new members and, in turn, share teachings and offer ritual ceremonies publicly. This process could include things such as empowerments (dbang) into practices associated with various tantric deities.

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– Yes

Notes: Historically speaking, Tibet is generally described as a theocracy. In the case of Central Tibet, this took on the form of the Dalai Lama leading both the religious and secular affairs of Tibetan peoples from the fifteenth century onward. On a regional scale, the relationship between secular and religious leadership mirrored that of the central government. In the case of the great Nyingma monasteries, such as Katok, Payul, and Mindroling, they received financial support from and/or acted as the regional political power. When the regional monastic institution did not hold overt power, the relationship is/was often described through the rubric of priest and patron, with the former offering religious guidance in return for financial support from the latter. This mirrors the historical situation of monastic and lay communities in early Indian Buddhist history.

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– Yes

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– Yes

Notes: The answer to this question is nuanced. Depending on the geographic region and historical time period, the religious leadership and polity could be one and the same. However, regardless of the location and era, the relationship between these two bodies is closely connected.

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– Yes

Notes: The answer depends on the geographical location and historical period. Looking back at the earliest days of the Nyingma lineage, the second great religious king of Tibet, Trison Detsen, was considered an important religious figure as well as political leader. This extends throughout history, however, over the centuries, with the strengthening of power in Central Tibet via the tradition of the Dalai Lamas, power was extricated from religious leaders (including those in the Nyingma lineage) in favor of appointed political figures.

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– No

Notes: The reality is that there are most likely historical examples of persecution from the polity for failure to observe religious acts/holidays/observances. However, I can not speak to this with accuracy as the information we have does not verify one view or the other. I am also reluctant to say the "field doesn't know" as there are views on both sides.

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– Yes

Notes: Tibetan political views of ethics are deeply informed by, and at times homologous with religious ethics. Ideals emphasize altruism and compassion as the underpinnings of ethical conduct.

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– Yes

Notes: In cases where the religious leadership and polity are not one-in-the-same, this is true throughout Tibetan history. Religious leaders were treated as living Buddhas and/or bodhisattvas, exemplifying the religious tradition and, in turn, necessitating preferential treatment. Treating a monastic affiliate well was considered one of the highest moral obligations.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Notes: This is very rare in Tibetan history, even cases of individuals leaving one lineage to join another.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 2000000

Notes: This number is calculated based on a roughly equal split of total Tibetan Buddhists (8 million) between the four major sects/lineages.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 25

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: The written corpus of the Nyingma lineage is as vast as any in the world. It consists of texts composed over a twelve hundred year period, beginning with Padmasambhava in the ninth century, the one who is credited with bringing a comprehensive form of Buddhism to Tibet. The corpus is generally broken into texts that explicate some combination of the view (Ita ba), meditation (sgom pa), and application (spyod pa) of the teachings.

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

Notes: This is perhaps the most important form of scripture within the Nyingma context. Referred to as pith instructions (man ngag), oral teachings are passed from teacher to student and constitute the large majority of esoteric teachings. In particular, as one progresses along the path, achieving higher and higher forms of soteriological understanding, the teachings are more often administered orally. This also emphasizes the intimacy of the Nyingma lineage, with the transmission of teachings often occurring in one-to-one environments.

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– No

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– Yes

Notes: There is a category of scripture called treasures (gter ma) that were hidden by Padmasambhava and his chief disciples to be revealed at a later date. It is claimed that this process of discovery and/or revelation occurred iteratively throughout history when the karmic causes and conditions were ripe for that particular teaching. The individuals who revealed these treasures were not supernatural in the sense of other-worldly birth, for example, but they are supernatural insofar as they needed to reach lofty soteriological states to perceive and/or understand the procedures of revelation. More information on this style of revelation can be found in: *Hidden Teachings of Tibet: An Explanation of the Terma Tradition of Tibetan Buddhism* by Tulku Thondup.

↳ Inspired by high god:

– No

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– Yes

Notes: There are imperceptible beings, such as Sky-goers (mkha' 'gro), who support the practice and achievement of practitioners within the Nyingma lineage. They often appear in dreams and/or visions at times of great difficulty and challenge. In the revelation process, they are often accredited as the mediums through which these "hidden" texts are revealed.

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– No

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Percentage: 10

Notes: Every settlement in the greater Tibetan Buddhist world would have had multiple stupas (mchod rten). These are often positioned at the entrances into settlements as well as major intersections. They are positioned in these places due to the fact that people frequently visit them, hence providing many opportunities to go near stupas, which is considered a meritorious act.

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 7500

Notes: This is based on the great Boudhanath Stupa in Kathmandu, Nepal. While outside the designated area of most adherents to the Nyingma lineage, it is nonetheless considered part of their religious world. This is, in large part, due to the fact that the lineage's founder Padmasambhava, as well as many other important religious figures, visited this place.

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 40

Notes: This is also based on the Boudhanath Stupa. Please see answer above for explanation

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Height, square meters: 250

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 12

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Percentage of area: 10

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

Notes: Bodies are most often cremated in Tibetan culture. Stupas (common religious monuments in the Tibetan Buddhist world) often contain the ashes, and/or relics from the cremation. In certain instances, great religious figure's entire bodies can be enshrined inside stupas. This occurs when a person (usually senior religious figure) gains a level of enlightenment that allows them to transcend the biological decomposition process, preserving their body in scientifically unexplainable ways.

↳ Cemeteries:

– No

Notes: Bodies are almost always cremated.

↳ Temples:

– Yes

Notes: Temples are ubiquitous throughout the Tibetan world. It is traditionally said that the second eldest male in each family was sent to join the religious order. Monks and/or nuns are usually in charge of overseeing local temples in villages and cities, providing religious guidance to, and performing religious rituals for the local population.

↳ Altars:

– Yes

Notes: It is customary for every adherent of the Nyingma lineage to have an altar (or shrine) in their home to which they say prayers and make offerings to daily.

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

Notes: The most common form of religious monument is the stupa. This is a dome shaped edifice often serving as a reliquary of a past religious figure. They are ubiquitous throughout the greater Tibetan cultural region.

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

Notes: These are often monastic and/or temple grounds, or the space around stupas in which people will congregate for celebrations.

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: Embedded in nearly every form of architecture, whether it be homes or commercial buildings, religious architecture is used.

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

- On persons
- At home
- All public spaces

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– Yes

Notes: In the Nyingma lineage's meditation systems, the eyes and process of seeing is considered the gateway for realization, or awakening. In turn, iconographically, the eyes become a particularly important aspect of statues and/or paintings. Eyes are often striking in appearance, bright and wide open exemplifying their meditation systems.

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: Mythic animals, such as the garuda, are essential to Tibetan Buddhist iconography in general, and within the Nyingma lineage.

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings are said to permeate the ecology of the planet and, in turn, many aspects of nature are codified in symbolic systems. The best example is Mount Kailash in western Tibet which is considered to be a naturally occurring stupa.

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: Nyingma religious figures are often attributed with supernatural powers and depicted posthumously as supernatural beings.

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: The most ubiquitous image within Tibetan Buddhist iconography is the Wheel

of Life (srid pa'i 'khor lo). In it, the lord of death holds cyclic existence ('khor ba) within which the six realms of beings—hell beings, hungry ghosts, animals, humans, demi-gods, and gods—are depicted. These are considered the possible future rebirths one can gain after death.

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Yes

Notes: There are numerous sacred symbols within Tibetan Buddhist iconography that have direct correlation with doctrine. Perhaps the most well known example is the sword of the Bodhisattva Manjushri (jam dpal dbyang), which is said to depict the discerning aspect of wisdom.

↳ Humans:

– Yes

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Yes

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Notes: The physical ecology is considered to reflect internal qualities of the mind and, in turn, it is considered sacred. In turn, Nyingma adherents rely on the environment to provide inspiration in their religious practice. The greatest example being the vistas of Tibet. They are considered sacred insofar as they reflect the internal expanse of mind.

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: Pilgrimage is at the heart of Tibetan culture and, in turn, it is vital to the Nyingma lineage. Beginning with the historical founder of the lineage--Padmasambhava--the locations in which masters practiced were viewed as sacred and worship in such a way. Following in the south Asian tradition of circumambulating a great master or monarch when greeting them, the term for pilgrimage in Tibetan nekhor literally means rounding (khor) sacred sites (ne). It is said within most Tibetan cultural settings that going on pilgrimage to mount Kailash--the center of the Tibetan cosmological universe--and rounding it three times is of highest importance.

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– Optional (common)

Notes: While not obligatory, pilgrimage to sacred sites is considered one of the most meritorious actions that adherents of the Nyingma lineage specifically, and Tibetan Buddhism in general can undertake.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: At its most basic level, a sentient being is described as having a body (or form) and mind. This varies depending on where they are located and how they manifest. For example, there are beings in imperceptible worlds/realm that may have entirely different “bodies” than animals possess. The mind is said to remain after the death of the physical body.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– Yes [specify]: The most common way to describe the relationship between spirit/mind and body is that of a horse (body) and rider (mind)--they are connected and can influence each other, yet, they are distinct.

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– No

Notes: There is no specific location for the afterlife as the Nyingma lineage adheres to a belief of rebirth. In turn, when one is reborn, the realms and/or worlds where this takes place are diverse in location and manifestation.

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

↳ In a human form:

– Yes

↳ In animal/plant form:

– Yes

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s):

– No

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage. etc.):

– No

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma):

– Yes

Notes: This is one of the defining characteristics of Buddhism in general, and specifically the Nyingma lineage of Tibetan Buddhism. Causality is the mechanism by which the cycle of existence ('khor ba) is perpetuated. However, while it is the perpetuating force, causality is not transcendent, but rather can be transcended.

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world:

– No

Notes: However, there are other forms which one can reincarnate in other worlds, such as gods, demi-gods, hungry ghosts, and hell beings.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

↳ Cremation:

– Yes

↳ Mummification:

– No

Notes: However, there are rare cases where bodies will naturally mummify over time due to the spiritual realization of an individual.

↳ Interment:

– No

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

↳ Feeding to animals:

– Yes

Notes: Sky burial is a common alternative to cremation within Tibetan culture in general, and the Nyingma lineage in particular. This is usually done on high plateaus where vultures are numerous.

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

Notes: It is common to cremate a religious adherent with their ritual implements, such as a bell, dorje (thunderbolt-like object), rosary, and more.

↳ Valuable items:

– No

Notes: Not unless their ritual implements are particularly valuable.

↳ Other grave goods:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Notes: As mentioned above, bodies are usually cremated. There are great formal processes for this undertaking.

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings and occurrences are vital to both Tibetan culture and philosophy. In regard to the latter, the existence of and interaction with supernatural beings is evidence of a world beyond what we generally perceive. In the Nyingma lineage, for example, dakinis--supernatural beings who support one on the meditative path--are vital to one's ability to progress through soteriological stages.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– No

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: There are situations where people can be "captured" by evil spirits and occupy the body of someone. There are also instances where anthropomorphic spirits can be seen by humans.

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: The boundaries between spirits and humans are quite porous. In turn, it is common for spirits to physically and psychologically influence humans.

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Notes: The knowledge of supernatural beings varies greatly depending on the context of their particular existence. In this way, their knowledge could be limited--for example if someone is "caught" after they die and cannot separate from their body, and, in turn, family system, their knowledge could be limited to this space. In other instances, the restrictions could differ or not be present at all.

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Notes: This depends on the particular situation. Each spirit may have particular attributes depending on the situation and/or their karma.

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Notes: Spirits are often not restricted to the sensorial limitations that living humans are. I have been told by adherents of the Nyingma lineage, for example, that spirits can see through walls, hear from great distances, and impact people in a range of ways.

↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: This is difficult to say for sure, or perhaps give textual evidence of this. However, spirits are understood in a variety of ways in Tibetan culture and can take on different powers/abilities depending on the particular situation. Seeing the motivation of another would likely depend on certain factors, such as the relationship between the spirit and the living person.

↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):

– No

↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– No

↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:

– No

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Notes: I must disclaim this answer to say to the best of my knowledge.

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

Notes: This is quite important in a Tibetan Buddhist context. The mind continues from life to life and situation to situation. There can be residue from past experiences and/or lives. Spirits can retain memory of previous experiences and/or lives in this way.

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Spirits can experience the same range of emotions--positive, negative and neutral--that living humans can. It is often said, however, that they tend toward negative emotions as they are likely a spirit due to some blockage in their migration from one life to the next.

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits possess hunger:

– Yes

Notes: And, this hunger can influence the actions of the spirit. In brief, spirits can experience nearly every human emotion and/or experience.

↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: They can exhibit any feature imaginable. This is due to the co-arising of one's consciousness of the spirit and the actual spirit being perceived.

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Notes: Feeling, perceiving, and interacting with spirits in a Tibetan context is completely normal. It is pleasantly a part of everyday life. As compared to north American fear of ghosts, for example, in Tibetan culture one embraces the existence of and relationship with spirits.

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: Dreams have an important place in Tibetan Buddhist religious practice in general, and in the Nyingma lineage specifically. Dreams are often the place where important teachings are given and/or experiences are had. Importantly, what occurs in dreams can have profound impacts on waking life.

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

Notes: Spirits can possess living and dead humans. In the latter example, the dead can re-emerge and "live" for another period possessed by spirits.

↳ Through divination processes:

– No

↳ Only through specialists:

– No

Notes: While it is not limited to specialists, there are various mediums who communicate with spirits in and through ritual practices. They are often called upon to help the family and/or loved ones of a spirit. As mentioned above, the existence of a spirit is generally related to obstacles in the transition from one life to the next. In this way, a specialist can help release a spirit from this situation.

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Communicate with living through other means:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: Spirits can take on a range of anthropomorphic, animalistic, and ecological forms. This is seen in the earliest myths of Buddhism coming to Tibet which include the subjugation of demons and demonesses in order to allow the religion to take root.

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Notes: These beings would have similar causal relationships as humans and other living beings.

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: They experience the world in similar ways to living beings.

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

Notes: Just as with the perceptible realms (khams), such as humans and animals, supernatural beings also possess hierarchy. It is only rarely mentioned, however, and open for interpretation.

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– No

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: The relationship between the supernatural and the human realm is dependent on humans' confusion and/or delusion. This confusion/delusion allows for the existence of the world as we know it, including the existence of supernatural beings. The technology that dictates social norms and their subsequent infractions is the law of karma, however, there are examples, at least within villages of Tibet, where supernatural beings are believed to be involved in the unfolding of the law of karma. Just to be clear, however, this is not true in the ultimate sense as anything contained within cyclic existence is understood to be non-inherently existent and, like mentioned above, based on confusion/delusion. To be clear, this section is not based on my textual understanding, but lived experience with adherents of the Nyingma lineage and tales of "old" Tibet that I've heard.

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: On the ground, in Tibetan communities, there are beliefs in supernatural beings reacting adversely due to people not following social norms. The idea is that acting out of turn brings things out of balance.

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Notes: This is true in the sense that they would care about murder in general. The supernatural beings, especially those embedded in the ecology of Tibet respond to actions done by humans.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

Notes: This is true insofar as all murders would be monitored. Whether the person murdered person adhered to any particular religion could elicit a response, but it would be circumstantial.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

Notes: This is true insofar as all murders would be monitored.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

Notes: There are responses to sexual behavior by supernatural beings. And, this is as dependent on the individuals own anxieties as is it on anything. If the adulterer is nervous about their actions, then it could result in a supernatural being acting adversely toward them.

↳ Incest:

– Yes

Notes: Insofar as they care about sexual activities in general.

↳ Other sexual practices:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

Notes: This is an interesting point in the Nyingma lineage. There are religious commitments, what could be considered oaths, taken by adherents and breaking these commitments is considered to be a terrible action. In turn, there are a whole range of subsequent outcomes that are described, many of them leading to harm of the person who committed the infraction--at times due to supernatural beings.

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

Notes: This is true in the sense that there are supernatural beings that are said to aid one on the path of meditation. In turn, if someone is acting lazily, they could act in such a way that motivates the person to continue.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

Notes: Views like this are embedded within Tibetan cultural practices that honor elders. Should one disrespect elders, there is a general view that some bad outcome could unfold in their life, some of which could be dependent on supernatural beings.

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

Notes: Gossip is considered a moral infraction in many instances. In turn, there are instances of belief in negative outcomes befalling someone who participates in gossip, some of which could be dependent on supernatural beings.

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Notes: This is an important element to ritual practice within the Nyingma lineage. For example, adhering to rituals based on the lunar calendar is expected and failure to do so could result in

negative karmic effects. And, within these outcomes, some of them may be dependent on supernatural beings.

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

Notes: This is an important element to ritual practices within the Nyingma lineage. For example, a small amount of food and/or drink is offered periodically during ritual practices in service of appeasing the local supernatural beings. This relationship is considered reciprocal insofar as the supernatural beings would support the ritual should they receive proper offerings.

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: On the relative level, like all of Tibetan Buddhism, the Nyingma lineage adheres to the view of karma: causes give rise to subsequent effects. Rewards and punishments are predicated on one's personal actions, as well as those of their communities. However, there are cases where supernatural beings are alleged to be responsible for some of the "punishment" that people experience.

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: The primary figure that is (at least figuratively) viewed as the agent of punishment is Yama, the god of death. This supernatural being oversees the six realms

of beings. The "agents" responsible within the human realm can vary. Supernatural beings are present throughout the natural world, for example, and can be responsible for adverse weather experiences should certain rituals not be followed, etc.

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

Notes: This is the heart of the Tibetan Buddhist in general, and at least a certain aspect of the Nyingma belief system. Karma, cause and effect is the primary modality through which effects (both punishments and rewards) unfold.

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: Each of these answers (and many more) can be understood as the "reasons" for punishment--or, more broadly negative outcome. All of these outcomes are karmic outcomes. All supernatural beings would be contained within cyclic existence, which is juxtaposed with liberation from cyclic existence, which is free from the law of karma, cause and effect.

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

Notes: All of the outcomes are based on the law of karma, cause and effect.

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: The descriptions of the suffering in hell realms are spectacular and horribly displeasing. This suffering is overseen by supernatural beings (albeit still contained in cyclic existence and not ultimately real).

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– Yes

Notes: Every action that one undertakes effects both this life and subsequent reincarnations afterward. These outcomes are dependent on the law of karma, however, embedded within the confusion of karma there can exist (ultimately unreal, but nonetheless believed in) supernatural beings. If one believes in such supernatural beings, they can be involved in the transition and selection of a subsequent life. This can result in the birth as an inferior life form and/or in an inferior realm.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Yes

Notes: "Yes," however, bad luck would be framed in and through a lens of karma, cause and effect. In this way, they might not use the frame of luck, but it would function similarly.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Yes

Notes: This would be dependent on the person acting being embedded within the political realm. If someone is, for example, a farmer, there would likely not be any political implications based on their actions.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– Yes

Notes: This would be dependent on the actor being engaged in battle, of course, and would be rare.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Yes

Notes: As primarily an agrarian culture, this is the biggest way in which supernatural beings impact the human existence. There are a whole range of beliefs that if one does not act according to certain prescribed norms then the ecological supernatural beings could act out in and through the weather.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– Yes

Notes: This is perhaps the second most common way in which supernatural beings impacts the human realm. Traveling in the Tibetan plateau is trepidatious and, in turn, many people are injured and/or die in travel. Many of these examples are explained in and through the actions of supernatural beings.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: This is true in and through disease and/or lack of food.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: There are examples of describing the suffering people experience in and through the lens of supernatural beings being upset and, in turn, inflicting sometimes extreme pain on people.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

Notes: See note above. Many illnesses are accredited within the Tibetan medicinal system to spirits occupying and/or negative impacting someone. These supernatural beings are exorcised in and through ritual practices.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– Yes

Notes: There are examples of infertility being described as supernatural beings negatively impacting someone who has committed a wrong.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– I don't know

Notes: This could be true, but I have not heard of such an example.

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– Yes

Notes: The coming of the next Buddha, Maitreya Buddha (the Buddha of Loving-kindness) is prophesized throughout literature in Tibetan Buddhism in general, and the Nyingma lineage in particular. Some of these predictions are not necessarily date driven, but rather dependent on certain causes and conditions arising. For example, one criteria is that the next Buddha will appear when the teachings of the current Shakyamuni Buddha no longer exist. When this happens, specifically, is not said. In other cases, the exact date (aeons from now) is given. The next Buddha is said to be in the pure realm of Akanishta currently and is preparing to descend into this world. Every Buddha that comes is said to display awakening in Bodhgaya, India at the Unbreakable throne (Varjasana).

↳ Alive, identified:

– No

Notes: The next Buddha is not alive in the sense of being a human in this realm. However, they are presently in the Akanishta pure realm existing based on the laws of that particular place. The laws of pure realms do not resemble human existence, necessarily, so categorizing the next Buddha as alive is problematic.

↳ Coming in this lifetime:

– No

Notes: The dates given are always for millennia in the future.

↳ Coming on specified date:

– Yes

Notes: As mentioned above, there are a range of prophecies for the coming of the next Buddha. Many claim it is at the end of this current age, which is millennia in the future. Others base their predictions on indicators, such as the Buddhist teachings no longer being extant in this realm.

↳ Coming in unspecified time in near future:

– No

↳ Coming in unspecified time in distant future:

– No

↳ Coming has already passed:

– No

Notes: However, there have been claims by individuals after 1959 that they are the next Buddha, however these people are outside the Nyingma lineage. One such example is Ram Bonjan Bahadur, or the Buddha Boy, in central Nepal who claims to be the Maitreya Buddha.

↳ One in a line of many past and future messiahs:

– Yes

Notes: The next Buddha is prophesized as a single example of a long line of Buddhas, with many having come in the past and many more to come in the future.

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– No

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– Yes

Notes: As mentioned above, Maitreya Buddha will return to re-establish the Buddhist religion in this realm. He is said to emphasize loving-kindness as his primary medium for communicating the entirety of the Buddhist path.

↳ Other purpose:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– No

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, however, it is considered to be an event in a cycle of ends and beginnings that have gone on for many aeons and will continue into the future.

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at some other time:

– No

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:

– No

↳ Divine judgment event:

– No

↳ Restoration of the world:

– No

Notes: However, as mentioned above, the eschaton is embedded within a series of cycles of creation/arising and destruction/end of many ages.

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:

– Yes

↳ Establishment of a new political system:

– No

↳ Establishment of a new religious system:

– Yes

Notes: It is said that the future age will be defined by loving-kindness (byams pa). However, this will still be embedded in the frame work of the Buddhist religion.

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The answer is really yes and no. Within the Nyingma lineage's presentation of the religious life, there are numerous stages and/or orientations of practice that, at times, differ considerably. They are based on the according level and/or capabilities of a specific adherent. In the basic, entry-level practices appropriate for those of lesser capabilities, the emphasis is put on prescribed action, whereas in the later, more advanced levels, appropriate for those of greater capabilities, the emphasis is on the ways in which they see the world.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The ethics found in the Nyingma lineage are embedded within cultural frameworks and, at times, there can be conventional moral distinctions, whereas at other times, the two—conventional vs moral—become one and the same. Ultimately, even the moral category is not considered to be universal or constant as all ethical activity is considered to be provisional. This latter belief is shared throughout Tibetan culture, however, narratives advocating for adherence to ethical norms are much more prevalent.

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Present and clear

Notes: At times, these distinctions are made clear and the cultural influence on ethics is explicated, especially by religious leaders.

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– Yes

Notes: Tibetan Buddhist metaphysics are complex. This is due to many factors, but most of all it is due to the fact that what they consider to be the end of physical concepts and the beginning of metaphysical concepts differ considerably from normative views in the West. In many ways, the law of karma could be considered metaphysical as it connects a being from life to life. Believes in interconnectedness between beings could also be categorized as metaphysical as it is believed that one's actions can have ripple effects to imperceptible beings at large distances and even different dimensions/realms.

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:
– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):
– Yes

Notes: The belief in karma is at the core of Tibetan Buddhism's understanding of ethics and morality. This forms the basis for many religious practices and/or trainings that are advocated for. It is, however, personal, insofar as karma is dependent on the individuals' and/or groups' shared confused and deluded beliefs. In turn, the law of karma is interconnected with the individual and communal group they are part of.

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:
– Yes

Notes: There are folk-style beliefs by adherents of Tibetan Buddhism that incorporate anthropomorphic spirits and they can be involved in the outcomes of especially negative karmic actions.

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:
– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:
– No

Notes: See explanations above

↳ Moral norms apply to:
– All individuals within society

Notes: As explained above, moral norms are culturally imbued and, in turn, they change over time. What is considered morality just in one period could be seen as unjust in another. This is due to the relativity of morality within a Tibetan cultural frame.

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Please note that all of these virtues are advocated for within the Nyingma lineage in a provisional context. In the end, all virtue and non-virtue dissolve.

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: An compelling component of the Nyingma lineage is that there are strands of monasticism (requiring celibacy) and laity (non-celibate) that are both viewed as legitimate vocations.

– Yes

Notes: This would be for an novice or fully-ordained monastics (male and female).

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males):

– No

↳ Monogamy (females):

– No

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: Celibacy for monastics. For laity, if a tantric practitioner sexual relations are considered a means for liberation. In these cases, there are various rules and/or approaches.

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Notes: Celibacy for monastics. For laity, if a tantric practitioner sexual relations are considered a means for liberation. In these cases, there are various rules and/or approaches.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: There are specific practices that require periodic fasting. One such example within the Nyingma lineage (also shared within the other lineages of Tibetan Buddhism) is a two-day fasting ritual (smyung gnas). These practices are observed for various reasons and at various times. The primary function of them are to serve as purificatory rituals, to either purify negative karma of this life or prevent one from going to the lower realms (i.e. hell, hungry-ghosts, and animal) in future lives.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Notes: Relationship to food and intoxicants varies within the Nyingma religion. While there is no prescribed requirements necessarily, there are various practices that emphasize how food/drink is consumed.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

↳ To other in-group members:

– No

↳ To out-groups:

– No

↳ Destroyed:

– No

↳ Other:

– Yes [specify]: To the religious leaders. When one is initiated within the lineage, it is expected that there will be offerings (often monetary) made in return.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: It is said within all lineages of Tibetan Buddhism and certainly the Nyingma lineage that the offering of one's practice (i.e. meditative, ritual, etc.) is the highest form of offering possible. So, in turn, one's time spent doing these practices are considered offerings (which I am loosely interpreting as a form of sacrifice).

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: This is universal throughout Tibetan Buddhism. When one enters into the religion, they are expected to adhere by certain ethical precepts. In the case of the Nyingma tradition, this is also true. In general, there are three levels of precepts: 1) individual liberation (Sanskrit: *prātimokṣa-saṃvara*; Tibetan: *so thar gyi sdom pa*); 2) bodhicatta/bodhisattva (*byang chub sems dpa' sdom pa*); and 3) tantra (*gsang sngags kyi sdom pa*).

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

- ↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):
Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.
– Hours: 1.5

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:
I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

- ↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:
– Number of participants: 200

- ↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):
Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.
– I don't know

- ↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.
– Yes
Notes: These are generally done by the attendants and/or supporters of those leading the ritual.

- ↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.
– Yes
Notes: These are generally done by the attendants and/or supporters of those leading the ritual.

- ↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:
– Yes

- ↳ Is there use of intoxicants:
– Yes
Notes: This depends on the type of ritual, but most tantric rituals require the ingesting of a small amount of ceremonial intoxicants.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Notes: There are various cloths that one would wear depending on their seniority and affiliation, but no permanent markers such as those mentioned here.

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Notes: This question is really on a case by case basis. As described above, the organizational structure of the Nyingma lineage has historically been de-centralized. In turn, there were many institutions that provided relief for challenges like famine, but it was not a centralized decision.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: We can safely say that throughout history local political leaders in Tibet also provided relief, along side the religious traditions.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Notes: While there was generalized poverty relief depending on the location and area, there is also a trope within Tibetan Buddhism at large and the Nyingma lineage specifically to provide care for young children who, at least provisionally, commit to the religious order.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Notes: There are contemporary cases, such as the Namdroling monastery in southern India, in which elderly homes are constructed for local people. Additionally, there are examples of elderly monks and nuns in each monastery/nunnery that are offered free lodging as they age.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– Yes

Notes: There were various types of formal education, mainly within the monastic institutions, and they did require ordination and/or initiation into the lineage.

Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Notes: There are examples where equal opportunities were offered to male and female adherents to the Nyingma lineage. However, these are not universal.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: Each monastery has a formal bureaucracy and each network of monasteries have formal bureaucratic systems in place.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: This is true in and around holidays as monastics would travel between monasteries in celebration. This is also the case in regard to lower-level and higher-level systems of bureaucracy.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Yes

Notes: This is true at least at the level of the specific institution. Monasteries would often store large amounts of food. Whether or not it was a service provided to the public is rarely spoken of.

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Yes

Notes: This is an interesting question. Religious institutions really functioned as members of society and in the Tibetan plateau, water management systems were some of the most complex in history and, in turn, the institutions participated.

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Notes: However, this answer must be contextualized. The "taxes" were often viewed as offerings to the religious group. In turn, one could answer "no" to this question and say that the exchange is not a tax due to not being required.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Local political institutions certainly collected taxes at varying levels throughout history.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Notes: There were cases in history that informal institutionalized police force-like bodies acted for various purposes.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: This depends on the specific local political institution, however, most if not all had police forces.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Depending on the location and era, there were varying types of judicial systems created by the local political institution.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

Notes: However, this was often (if not always) informal.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: This is dependent on the locale and era in which one is looking. Various places and time periods had different levels of legal codes.

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– Yes

↳ Does the religious group in question have the power to conscript:

– No

↳ Does the religious group in question maintain a full-time military corps (e.g. Swiss Guard):

– No

↳ Does the religious group in question maintain a standing army:

– No

Notes: The existence of standing armies in religious institutions depends heavily on the time period. There were eras where inter-religious warfare was prevalent and, in turn, for short periods, standing military may have been maintained.

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Most often, religious adherents did not participate in military service.

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Local and regional military existed to various degrees throughout Tibetan history.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: The language the Nyingma lineage was shared with all people of the Tibetan plateau. Regional differences did exist.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Tibetan language found its origins primarily in the translation of south Asian religious scripture. In turn, it is claimed to be particularly strong in communicating religious questions/topics.

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: The lunar calendar is intricately linked to the practice structure of the Nyingma lineage.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The central government of Tibet and regional powers would have shared the same lunar calendar containing many, if not all, religious holidays.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Notes: Historically, Nyingma religious institutions were supported by the laity, however, a certain portion of their food was produced onsite.

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Notes: As noted above, there is an important symbiosis between formal religious adherents and the laity. In turn, a large portion of the religious institutions food was provided by the laity.

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